

[1] A.1 " 1. FIRST OBSERVATIONS WITH THE NEW TRANSIT CIRCLE
Nov 7(?) 1848 to July 30, 1849 "

[pp 443-535]

annotated in May, 1854. (p. 443)

[2] A.2 " 2. TRANSIT CIRCLE 1849
July 30 to SEPT 25 "

[536-629]

"A. H." - Nov. 25, 1859 (p. 536)

[3] A.3 " TRANSIT CIRCLE SEPT. 26, 1849 to
Nov. 29, 1849 "

[1-88]

"WCB" - Nov 2, 1849 (p. 56)

p. 69: "List of Chronometers employed on the expedition
for ascertaining the difference of meridians of
Greenwich + Cambridge."

[4] A.4 " TRANSIT CIRCLE Nov. 30, 1849 to
FEB. 6, 1850 "

[89-184]

"23 H. Refraction" - (p. 142)

observers - (p. 162)

[5] A.5 "TRANSIT CIRCLE FEB 6, 1850 to
APRIL 30, 1850"

[185-286]

"Prof. Peirce" - (p. 208)

[6] A.6 "TRANSIT CIRCLE May 1, 1850 to
Oct. 20, 1850"

[287-384]

"⁵ ^A
300-400
having new assistant" - p. 315 Chas. Tuttle.
"communications workshop" - p. 351 800 letters/week

[7] A.7 "TRANSIT CIRCLE FROM ~~OCT~~ DEC. 21, 1850 to
DEC. 26, 1850"

[385-480]

[8] A.8 "TRANSIT CIRCLE FROM DEC. 26, 1850 to
APRIL 3, 1851 - (Vol. II)"

[481-574]

p. 506 - "1851 Jan 21
"First transmission of
tone to Boston by the Electric
Telegraph"

[9] A.9 "Transit Circle from April 3, 1851 to
July 13, 1851"
[1-95]

[10] A.10 "Transit Circle from July 13, 1851 to Sept. 5, 1851
contains measures of the Observatory"
[96-191]

(127~~7~~⁸ - Eclipse of the Sun July 27/28
+128) (photographs - Daguerrotypes)

(178) Measures taken at the Obs. Aug. 30th

[11] A.11 "Transit Circle from Sept. 5, 1851 to
Jan. 15, 1852"
[192-285]

(214) List of Astronomical records
of their distances from the Sun
for Edinburg, Scotland, Aug. 26, 1851.

[12] A.12 "(value of level divisions) Transit Circle from
Jan 15, 1852 to June 28, 1852"
[286-390]

(p 317) - The Spring Gw. was
surrounded by a great many
visitors during the observed
Spring Gw. out of order.

[12] continued

(377) June 23, 1852

"After this date the reductions
see in the transit book.

Previous to this date for
reductions, see two separate
books A & B & Chron. Exped.

[13]

A. 13

"Transit Correct from June 28 to Dec 5/6, 1852."

[391-488]

(419) Aug 3, 1852 Power in transit
circle changed from 56 to 153.

Ver Transit } observed
For Dry Circle } included

[14]

A. 14

"Transit Circle from Dec. 1 1852 to July 8, 1853
- (Magnetic Variation 1708 to 1852)."

[489 - 583]

(489-495) Speed of Sound Experiments.

Genl Charles Keilber USN

(576) Magnetic Declination of London,

1806-1856

[15] A.15 "Transit Circle from July 8, 1853 to Feb. 26, 1854
- (Vol IV) "
[1-91]

[16] A.16 "Transit Circle from Feb. 28, 1854 to Aug 15, 1854 "
[92-189]

(118) Magnetic Needle Dip - Leind Whipple's
Surveying Expedition - May 10, 1854

[17] A.17 "Transit Circle Aug 15/16 to Nov. 27th 1854 "
(1st observations of Zero Stars by T.C.) "
[190-283]

[18] A.18 "Transit Circle Nov. 27, 1854 to Jan. 25, 1855
[284-376]

[19] A.19 "Transit Circle Jan 25, 1855 - May 6, 1855 "
[unnumbered]
telegram correspondence between Hess &
Caj's College Frederick W. B
Feb. 2, Feb. 10

[20] A.20 "Transit Circle May 6, 1855 - July 31, 1855"

[21] A.21 "(Howard) Transit Circle Aug. 1, 1855 - Sept. 25, 1855"

[22] A.22 "Transit Circle from Sept 25, 1855 - March 27, 1856"

(Sept. 25) - "The gallery of England is
delighted. No Britisher ever saw
that star from her native isle."
"Set it down w/ gold or besting
fellows."

March - "A winter of relentless constancy."

[23] A.23 "Transit Circle from March 27, 1856 to June 15/6 1856"

[24] A.24 "Transits. June 16, 1856 to Sept. 5, 1856"

[25] A.25 "(Names of the Astronomers + observations of Venus)
Transits from Sept. 5, 1856 to Feb 9, 1857"

[26] A.26 "Transit Circle . New Group of Five Lesies. from Feb. 17, 1857
to Sept. 21st 1857 (from Feb. 17 to March 4, 1857 copied
from another Book)"

[27] A.27 "Transit Circle ~~to~~ Sept. 21st 1857 to Nov 3 1857"
(cover notation: "Moon Calculations to be
observed for War Dept.")

[28] A.28 "Transit Circle Nov. 3 1857 to Feb. 10, 1858"

[29] A.29 "Transit Circle Feb. 10, 1858 to July 5, 1858"

[30] A.30 "Transit Circle July 5, 1858 to Jan 24, 1859"

[31] A.31 "Transit Circle Jan. 24, 1859 to Aug 17, 1859"
(Apr. 20 and 15/20 - error analysis
A. H. - frequency table in
estimate
and graph)

[32] A.32 "Transit Circle Aug 17, 1859 to Jan 23, 1860"

- [33] A.33 "Transit Instrument Jan 23, 1860 to June 23, 1860"
- [34] A.34 "Transit Instrument June 23, 1860 to Nov. 29, 1860"
(Oct. 26, 1859) "New E.C. - Dbl. End +
Hydraulic Escapement"
- [35] A.35 "Transit Circle Nov. 29, 1860 - March 21, 1861"
- [36] A.36 "Transit Circle March 21, 1861 to Oct. 1, 1861"
- [37] A.37 "Transit Circle Oct. 1, 1861 to March 25, 1862"
- [38] A.38 "Meridian Circle March 28, 1862 to May 7, 1862"
- [39] A.39 "Meridian Circle May 7, 1862 - Aug. 6, 1862"
- [40] A.40 "Meridian Circle Aug. 11, 1862 + Sept. 25, 1862"

- [41] A. 41 "Meridian Circle Sept. 27, 1862 to Dec. 8, 1862"
- [42] A. 42 "Meridian Circle Dec. 10th 1862 to Feb 16, 1863"
- [43] A. 43 "Meridian Circle Feb. 17 1863 to May 25, 1863"
- [44] A. 44 "Meridian Circle May 28, 1863 to Aug. 14, 1863"
- [45] A. 45 "Meridian Circle Aug. 14, 1863 to Sept. 22, 1863"
- [46] A. 46 "Meridian Circle Sept. 23, 1863 to Dec. 3, 1863"
- [47] A. 47 "Meridian Circle Dec. 5, 1863 to Jan. 11, 1864"
- [48] A. 48 "Meridian Circle Jan. 11, 1864 to March 3, 1864"
- [49] A. 49 "Meridian Circle March 7, 1864 to April 29, 1864 (cont to 9-16)"
- [50] A. 50 "Meridian Circle Apr 2-16, April 29 - May 18, 1864"

May 10 (The 2nd day of Sn. Class
was in the study while this
C. al. was going on, &
caused some confusion by stopping
the Chromograph.)

- [51] A.51 "Meridian Circle May 22 1864 to June 6th 1864"
- [52] A.52 "Meridian Circle June 7, 1864 to June 15th, 1864"
- [53] A.53 " (unlabeled) [Meridian Circle June 21st 1864 to July 5th 1864"
- [54] A.54 "Meridian Circle July 6, 1864 to July 13th 1864"
- [55] A.55 "Meridian Circle July 20, 1864 to Sept. 9, 1864"
- [56] A.56 "Meridian Circle Sept. 10, 1864 to Oct. 10, 1864"
- [57] A.57 "Meridian Circle Oct. 10, 1864 to Nov. 4, 1864"
- [58] A.58 "Meridian Circle ~~Nov.~~ 10, 1864 to Nov. 23, 1864"
- [59] A.59 "Meridian Circle Nov. 25, 1864 to Dec. 20, 1864"
- [60] A.60 "Meridian Circle Dec. 30, 1864 to Jan. 18, 1865"

- [61] A.61 "Meridian Circle Jan 20, 1865 to Feb 1, 1865"
- [62] A.62 "Meridian Circle Feb 2, 1865 to Feb. 25, 1865"
- [63] A.63 "Meridian Circle Feb. 27, 1865 to Apr. 3, 1865"
- [64] A.64 "Meridian Circle Apr. 3, 1865 to Apr. 26, 1865"
- [65] A.65 "Meridian Circle ~~Apr~~ May 1, 1865 to June 2, 1865"
- [66] A.66 "Meridian Circle June 3, 1865 to July 4, 1865"
- [67] A.67 "Meridian Circle July 5, 1865 to July 18, 1865"
- [68] A.68 "Meridian Circle July 20, 1865 to Aug. 1, 1865"
- [69] A.69 "Meridian Circle Aug. 2, 1865 to Aug. 28, 1865"
- [70] A.70 "Meridian Circle Aug. 29, 1865 to Sept. 15, 1865"

- [71] A.71 "Meridian Circle Sept. 16, 1865 to Sept. 30, 1865"
- [72] B.1 "Reduction of Transits Jan. 1, 1849 to Aug. 16, 1849"
- [73] B.2 "Reduction of Transits Aug. 16, 1849 to Dec. 7, 1849"
- [74] B.3 "Reduction of Transits Dec. 7, 1849 to Apr. 2, 1850"
- [75] B.4 "Reduction of Transits Apr. 2, 1850 to Oct. 5, 1850"
- [76] B.5 "Reduction of Transits Oct. 5, 1850 to Dec. 30, 1850"
- [77] B.6 "Reduction of Transits Dec. 30, 1850 to Apr. 5, 1851"
- [78] B.7 "Reduction of Transits Apr. 5, 1851 to July 8, 1851"
- [79] B.8 "Reduction of Transits July 8, 1851 to Sept. 4, 1851"
- [80] B.9 "Reduction of Transits Sept. 4, 1851 to Nov. 11, 1851"

- [81] B.10 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 11, 1851 to Feb. 25, 1852"
- [82] B.11 "Reduction of Transits Feb. 25, 1852 to July 6, 1852"
- [83] B.12 "Reduction of Transits July 6, 1852 to Nov. 17, 1852"
- [84] B.13 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 17, 1852 to May 1, 1853"
- [85] B.14 "Reduction of Transits May 1, 1853 to Nov. 2, 1853"
- [86] B.15 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 2, 1853 to April 4, 1854"
- [87] B.16 "Reduction of Transits April 4, 1854 to Aug. 9, 1854"
- [88] B.17 "Reduction of Transits Aug 9, 1854 to Nov. 27, 1854"
- [89] B.18 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 27, 1854 to Jan 30, 1855"
- [90] B.19 "Reduction of Transits Jan 30, 1855 to May 6, 1855"

- [91] B.20 "Reduction of Transits May 6, 1855 to Aug 1, 1855."
- [92] B.21 "Reduction of Transits July 31, 1855 to Sept. 25, 1855"
- [93] B.22 "Reduction of Transits Sept. 25, 1855 to March 30, 1856"
- [94] B.23 "Reduction of Transits March 30, 1856 to June 11, 1856"
- [95] B.24 "Reduction of Transits June 11, 1856 to Aug. 22, 1856"
- [96] B.25 "Reduction of Transits Aug. 22, 1856 to Nov. 20, 1856"
- [97] B.26 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 20, 1856 to Apr. 30, 1857"
- [98] B.27 "Reduction of Transits Apr. 30, 1857 to Oct. 4, 1857"
- [99] B.28 "Reduction of Transits Oct. 4, 1857 to Nov. 28, 1857"
- [100] B.29 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 28, 1857 to Feb. 23, 1858"

- [101] B.30 "Reduction of Transits Feb. 23, 1858 to June 24, 1858"
- [102] B.31 "Reduction of Transits June 24, 1858 to Nov. 9, 1858"
- [103] B.32 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 9, 1858 to June 19, 1859"
- [104] B.33 "Reduction of Transits June 19, 1859 to Oct. 14, 1859"
- [105] B.34 "Reduction of Transits Oct. 14, 1859 to March 27, 1860"
- [106] B.35 "Reduction of Transits March 27, 1860 to Nov. 16, 1860"
- [107] B.36 "Reduction of Transits Nov. 16, 1860 to Jan. 1, 1861"
- [108] C.1 "North and South Meridian Merles and
level readings of Transit Circle"
[Dec. 5, 1849 - July 1, 1853]
- [109] C.2 "North and South Meridian Merles. July, 1853 - to April
21, 1855. Level readings of Transit Circle.
New Values of A + C Feb. 10, 1854.
"Constancy of Merles" (Azimuth, level, + Collateral errors + growths, falls
- [110] C.3 "North + South Meridian Merles and level Readings"
from Apr. 21, 1855 to Sept 8, 1856"

- [111] C.4 "Meridian Marks. Azimuth, $r = 2^{\circ} 285$
level, and Collimation of the Transit Circle 1856, Sept.
to Feb. 24, 1859 "
- [112] C.5 "Meridian Marks. Az. level + Coll cor. from
Feb. 24, 1859 to March 11, 1862."
- [113] C.8 "Instrumental Corrections 1863 Dec-29"
[Oct, 1865]
- [114] C.9 "Computed AR of Polar Stars
March 11, 1862 - Aug 19, 1863 "
- [115] C.10 "Computed AR of Polar Stars
Aug 22, 1863 - Nov. 18, 1864 "
- [116] C.11 "Chronograph Record June 1861 to July 1863"
- [117] C.12 "Chronograph Record
July 23, 1863 to Nov. 4, 1864 "
- [118] C.13 "Chronograph Record Nov. 10, 1864 to Sept 12, 1865 "
- [119] C.14 "Chronograph Record Sept 13, 1865 - [Feb. 20, 1866] "

[120] C.12 [C.15] "This book seems to belong to Series C. This
label was put upon it May 25, 1868 "

[Oct 2, 1865 - March 22, 1866] "note July 30, 1877. This book contains some of the same
observations found in A. 24, & others for date for which there is no record in A. 24
was when used for ..."

65/201-299

- [201] H. 47 " Σ July 6 to Aug 19, 1862 " Comets, Comans y B. Aguirre
- [202] H. 48 " Σ Aug 19 - to Dec 2, 1862 " Comet 1862 III and Leonis (72)
- [203] H. 49 " Σ Dec. 6, 1862 to Apr. 9, 1863 " Orion
(Letter April 11 - Dimensions y Dome)
- [204] H. 50 " Σ Apr. 13 to June 4, 1863 " Saturn + his Satellite
Comets.
- [205] H. 51 " Σ June 10, to Oct 1, 1863 " Saturn Satellite.
Comets
" Nebula of (?)
Feb 20, 1862
Main Planet
- [206] H. 52 " Σ Oct. 5, 1863 to Feb. 19, 1864 " Comets, Main Planet,
Orion (Zones)
- [207] H. 53 " Σ Feb 19 to March 21, 1864 " Sat. ^{satellite} Orion
March 3: Zodi Light
- [208] H. 54 " Σ March 21 to June 1864 " Orion, Main Planet,
Instrumental Errors.

[209] H.55 "E_p June 1864 to March 27, 1865" Mercur. Planets,
Mars (includ. Venetals)
Comets.

[210] H.56 "E_p Apr. 3, 1865 - (?)] Orion, Mercur. Planets, Comets
Feb. 5, 1866.

[211] K.1 "Zones 1852 Apr. 7 to May 4" (Zones 1-7)

[212] K.2 "Zones 1852 May 4 to Nov. 3" (Zones 7-13)

[213] K.3 "Zones 1852 Nov 4 to Dec. 14" (14-19, Bessel Zones)

[214] K.4 "Zones Dec 15, 1852 to Jan 8, 1853" (20-26)

[215] K.5 "Zones Jan 11, 1853 to (Feb 11, 1853)" (27-33)

[216] K.6 "Zones Feb 12, 1853 to March 15, 1853" (34-39) ~~3~~

[217] K.7 "Zones March 16 to Apr. 1, 1853" (40-45)

[218] K.8 "Zones April 8, 1853 to May 11, 1853" (46-54)

[219] K.9 "Zones May 31 to Sept 8, 1853" (55-62)

[220] K.10 "Zones Sept 27, to Dec. 8, 1854" (65-84)

[221] K.11 " Zones Dec. 8 '54 to Feb 3 '55" (84² - 88)

[222] K.12 " Zones Feb. 12 to Apr. 16, '55" (89 - 100)

[223] K.13 " Zones Apr. 23, to July 17, 1855" (101 - 116)

[224] K.14 " Zones March 30, 1859 to May 3, 1859" (1 - 6)

[225] K.15 " Zones May 3, 1859 - May 14, 1859" (6 - 7)
(May 23, 1859)

[226] K.16 " Zones May 23 to Aug 25, 1859" (117 - 124)

[227] K.17 " Zones Aug 29, to Nov 28, 1859" (125 - 135)

[228] K.18 " Zones Nov. 26, 1859 to Feb 17, 1860" (134 - 146)

[229] K.19 " Zones Feb 21 to Nov 24, 1860" (147 - 189) Catalogue des

[230] K.20 " Zones Nov. 20, 1860 to Feb 4, 1861"

[231] K.21 "Zones Feb 26 - April 8, 1861"

[232] K.22 "Zones Apr 8 to June 25, 1861"

[233] K.23 "Zones July 11, to Oct. 29, 1861"

[234] K.24 "Zones Sept 24, 1861 to Jan 31, 1862"

[235] K.25 "Zones Oct 22, 1862 to Feb 10, 1863"

[236] K.26 "Zones Feb 18, 1862 to May, 1864"

[237] K.27 "Zones June 23, 1864 to [Sept 27, 1864]"

[238] L.1 "Reduction of Zone Observations 1853" (Appendix Part. Zones 1-39)

[239] K.28 "Zones Oct 5, 1864 to [Dec. 1, 1864]"

[240] L.2 "Reduction of Zone Observations 1853" (Zones 40-60, 1-16)

~~23~~

[241] L.3 "Reduction of Zues Observations 1853" (Z 15-39)

[242] L.4 "Reduction of Zues 1853" (Z 40-56)

[243] L.5 "Reduction of Zues 1853" (Z 57-62)

[244] L.6 "Reduction of Zues Observations 1853" (Z 2-62)

[245] L.7 "Reduction of Zues Observations
 $0^{\circ} 20'$ to $0^{\circ} 40'$ - $17^{\text{h}} 50^{\text{m}}$ to $6^{\text{h}} 41^{\text{m}}$
Zues 63-92"

[246] L.8 "Reduction of Zues Obs's
 $0^{\circ} 20'$ to $0^{\circ} 40'$ - $6^{\text{h}} 33^{\text{m}}$ to
Zues 91-116"

[247] L.9 [Comparisons of Zues]

[248] L.10 "Reduction of Zues No Reduction 1853" (Chronograph record of Zues)

[249] L.11 "Reduction of Zues Comparison of Magnitudes 1852" (1 p.) (note in Chronograph)

[250] L.12 "Special Zues & Magnitudes.
Apr 23, 1862 to ?"

[251] L.13 "Revision of Zues. Magnitudes" (3p. note on reduction of magnitudes procedure at end)

[252] M. 2 "Reduction of Zones - I" (bound + printed forms)

* [253] M. 3 "Gould's Universal Index" (Catalogue?)

[254] M. 5 ~~4~~ (Tables, Procedures)

[255] M. 6 "Tables of Contents of Various Books Containing records of observations made with various instruments 1841-1855 or thereabouts." (note of explanation on page 185)

[256] M. 7 "Various Memoranda" (¹⁸⁴⁴ up to 1858) magnetic Measurements (esp. table Determinations, etc.)

[257] M. 9 "Catalogue Stars - 1854-58" (Transit Circle Obs.)

[258] M. 10 "Tables for approximating Instrumental Corrections" (~1855)

[259] M. 11 "Catalogue of Stars for Zones" (~1853)

[260] M. 12 "Reduction of all the Stars in Ulices from 0° to 1° ~~to 1854~~ to 1855

[261] M. 13 "Printing of Zue Obs's 1854 + History of Description of the Obs." (including list of ~~the~~ recipients)

[262] M. 14 Lists of Persons + Institutions, Recipients of the Annals of Harvard College Obs."

[263] M. 15 "Meteorological Jan 1, 1861 to [May, 1863]"

[264] M. 16 "1859-60 Comet Seeker Dec. ¹⁸⁵⁷ 1 to Sept. 11, 1860."

[265] M. 17 "Colorado Survey - Time" (Heard. Obs)
(Astronomical Computations) Dec 23, 1857 - May 23, 1858

[266] M. 18 "Colorado Survey - Latitude by Polaris" Dec 23, 1857 - May 23, 1858

[267] M. 19 "—" Jan 5, 1855 to May 2, 1855 (Solar Obs's)

[268] M. 20 "—" Catalogue of Bright Nebulae + Clusters (Comet hunting?)
[June 16, 1850 to May, 1853.]

[269] M. 21 (Comet Seeliger) June 10, 1847 to June 5, 1850

* [270] M. 23 "Books Received at the Obs. of H.C." (1862-1878)

[271] M. 24 "Reduction of Moon Culminations from Jan 1849 to —"
(May ²⁸, 1852)

[272] M. 25 "Reduction of Moon Culminations from July 1857 to (Oct 3, 1854)"
"Supplementary"

[273] M. 26 "P. S. ~~at~~" June 16, 1856 - July 4, 1856
(Drawings of star configurations + angles)

- [274] M. 27 (Nov 15 - 1860 to Aug 22, 1851) (Further? alerts at Keppel White Mountain)
- * [275] M. 28 "Gould's Universal Index" List of subscribers p. 298 → Public list. ^{cal} list + eds.
- [276] M. 29 "Prints 1860 to — (Dec 10, 1863) (prints in ^{any} unpaired)
- * [277] M. 30 "Memoranda for Obs. Report" Dec 7, 1861 to Dec. 31, 1864
- * [278] M. 31 "Memoranda" Jan 3, 1862 Jan 2, 1865
- * [279] M. 32 "Catalogue of Books in the Whalley's library commenced Oct 9, 1856"
- [280] M. 33 * Chronomet. Steps (also Lib) 1862-5
- [281] M. 34 "Mexican Catalogue"
- [282] M. 35 "Eclipse of April 25, 1846 Portland"
- * [283] M. 36 "Account of various Records + Papers belonging to the Observatory" (up to 1866)
- [284] N. 1 "Obs. w/ East Equatorial (Argues) N. 1 June 2 - July 6, 1866
- [285] N. 2 "Obs. w/ P. Eq. (Argues) N. 2 July 9 to July 22, 1866

- [286] N. 3 " obs. w/ E. S. (Aug.) No. 3 July 24 - Aug 4, 1866 "
- [287] N. 4 " obs. w/ E. S. (Aug.) No. 4 Aug 13 - Aug 25, 1866 "
- [288] N. 5 " " No. 5 Aug. 26 to Sept. 10, 1866 "
- [289] N. 6 " " No. 6 Sept. 12 - Oct. 3, 1866 "
- [290] N. 7 " " No. 7 Oct 2 - Oct 21, 1866 "
- [291] N. 8 " " No. 8 Oct 22, 1866 to Jan 19, 1867 "
- [292] N. 9 " " No. 9 Jan 23 - Apr 23, 1867 "
- [293] N. 10 " " No. 10 Apr. 25 - Oct, 24, 1867 "
- [294] N. 11 " " No. 11 Oct 25, 1867 to Jan 16, 1868 "
- [295] N. 12 " " No. 12 Jan 17, 1868 to Apr 1, 1868 "
- [296] N. 13 " " No. 13 Apr 1 - Oct 9, 1868 "
(Syracuse)
- [297] N. 14 " " No. 14 Oct 10 - Dec 19, 1868 "
- [298] N. 15 " " No. 15 Dec 22, 1868 Apr 22, 1869 "
- [299] N. 16 " " No. 16 Apr 28 to Oct 18, 1869 "

[121] D.1 "Minutes of Chronometer Expedition Commencing April 1849
Terminating Feby. 1850. No. 1"

[Laplace's determinant]

letter to Prof J. Woolloch from E. ^{W. P.} ~~W. P.~~ ^{Went Point}
Feb. 18, 1873

"I have been ordered to Washington to expect I ~~was~~ to go
out with some party to "Franklin-Rovers".

[122] E.1 "Meridian Circle Nov 7, 1859 to May 25, 1860"
[begin w/ 3 pages of directions] ^{description of procedure}

[123] E.2 "Meridian Circle May 24, 1859 to Nov. 3, 1859"

[124] E.3 "Meridian Circle May 25, 1860" - [Nov. 13, 1860]

[125] E.4 "Declinations. Dec 20, 1862 to Sept. 9 1863"
[1 p. description of procedure]

[126] E.5 "Declinations Sept 14, 1863 - " [Oct. 17, 1864]

[127] E.6 "New Albion's Meridian Circle from Feby 17, 1857 to ⁷
Scrap Book of observations on the Meridian Bars in
Declination Apr 24 to June 12, 1857"
[Obs. for May 25, 1858]

[128]

E.7

"Transit Circle 1851-2-3"

(C. W. Fittle)
Obs's of
Dec 6, 1851 to Nov 1851

[129]

E.8

"Transit Circle Cambridge Observatory
From Aug 7 to Dec 4, 1851"

Jan 12/13 1852

[12 hrs ahead in behavior
of stars to find stars
in clear sky.]

Nov. 18/18 "After observing
Lalande + Spica 2964 was not
aside, where it ought to have
been by age. Witness its
operations.

Feb. 17/13

"Problème alud, e
copinis collectis loco
geocentrico atque situ
planis orbitae eorum
locum heliocentricum
in orbita demonstrare."

[130]

F.1

"1845 Dec. to 1846 April

Moon Culminations + Transits"
"In Bieder's Comet"
[Comet also, too]
Feb-March New Comet

Dec. 18, 1852

"Observations de Cambridge
le 18 Decembre 1852
Il est une long seu
depuis je —

Oct 2/3 1853

"Voraussetzung - support
presumpt
Angabe - statement"

[131] F.2 "1846 April to Oct. # Comets + Meridian Transits"
June 5th [faces drawn]
Aug. 25 [earthquake]

[132] F.3 "Oct. 3¹⁸⁴⁶ to Apr. 16, 1847" (Meridian Transits).
[pp. 20 - 109]

[133] F.4 "April 24, 1847 - Feb. 9, 1848"
[pp. 120 - 284]

[134] F.5 "Feb. 18, 1848 - Aug, 1848"
[pp. 298 - 349] (Aug. 1, 1848)
made 14 Exposures !!!

[135] F.6 "No. 11"

p. 1 "Preliminary Selection of Stars used on the
Chromometric Expedition in 1849 = 50

Meridian Transits (Aug. 1, 1849 to Feb. 21, 1850)

[136] F.7 "Meridian and Prime Vertical Observations
Nov 6, 1844 to (Dec 11/12, 1844)"
(p.1) "The following obs were made w/ the
small instruments pertaining to the occupat
of the New Obs. in Summerhouse Hill -"

[137] F.8 "West Point Nov 5 1851 to (Dec 16/17, 1851)"

[138] F.9 "Prime Vertical Nov. 1854 to —"

[139] F.10 "Magnetic + Prime Vertical 1858"
[Sept 8, 1857 ~~Oct 9, 1858~~] Jan 24, 1859

[140] F.11 "Terrestrial Magnetism from March 25, 1858 to —"
[June 5, 1861]

[141] F.12^a ^{no title}
[June 5, 1864 - (Chronograph. July 21, 1864)]

[142] F.12^b "(Copy) Prime Vertical Computat of latitude 1864"

(last page of text) "The revision of this
work has been carried on, on
board the U S S Drumont where
weather is the exception to the
general condition of things. This
will explain the omissions
of this work W. A. R

[143] F.13 "Telegraph July 6 to Oct. 28, 1848"
[pp. 36-442] [p. 350 - Code]

[144] G.1 "Chronometers from Oct. 6, 1851 to July 1, 1853"

[145] G.2 "Chronometers from July 1, 1853"
(Annals Eclipse of May 26, 1854)
- Apr. 24, 1855

[146] G.3 "Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks, ^{Chronometer expedition} April 11, 1855 B'
and 12-minute comparators No. 1107 + 1506 + 1507"
(next page - ^{June Oct 1855} The Coast Survey Chronometer Expedition)

[147] G.4 "Sidereal + Mean Solar Clocks from Jan. 1, 1856 to Feb. 27, 1856
Mar. 19th - ¹⁸⁵⁶ Offer of Telegraph Installation.

[148] G.5 "Sidereal + Mean Solar Clocks from Feb. 28, 1857 to July 2, 1858
(test + repetition of "circulating" procedure)
H. Briggs

[149] G.6 "Sidereal + Mean Solar Clocks + Chronometer
July 2, 1856 to July 16, 1860"

[150] G.7 "Sidereal + Mean Time Clocks + Chronometer July 1860
to Sept 2/3, 1862"

[151] G.8 " — " [Sept. 16, 1862 - March 2, 1866]
(Chronometer?)
(Merits)

[152] G.^a " Rail Road Time Commenced June 29, 1854 to Oct. 1854

[153] G.^b " Trials of Pendulums + Chronometers "
[Apr. 27, 1857 - Feb. 19, 1859]

[154] H.^a " Vol I 517-604 Nov. 1848 - Feb. 1849
(interest, accounts) Comets + Double Stars 1848 (No 4) "

Measurements of Mr. Buldwin, Merit
+ Despatches
List of Observations.
Saturn's Rings
Jupiter.

[155] H.^a " Equatorial Reductions June 21 1860 to [Jan 23, 1861] "

[156] H.₁ " Vol T 1-80 1846 Oct to July 1847.

Equatorial.
pages

(Merits, Jupiter)
June 27/28 " 1st obs. w/ the
Great Refractor "

[157] H.2 " Vol I 81-168 1847 July to Dec. Equatorial "
[Sept 18 - P.N. obs.]
(Merits, Neptune, Venus
Andromeda Nebula)

Drawing

[158] H.3 "Vol. I 169-256 Dec. 1847 to Aug 1848"
Astr. Ned., Jup., Comets.
Letter By Peire
↳ Uranus Satellites

[159] H.4 "Vol. I 257-344 Nov. 1847 to Feb. 1848
Equator (Principes de...)"
(257) Powers of Eyepiece of Great Telescope
Mars, Orion Neb., Jup.

[160] H.5 "Vol. I 345-432 Feb. to Sept 1848 Equatorial
+ Prime Vertical"
Jup, Sat
410 (Plan of Obs. Grounds)
411 (Ground Plan of Obs. Building, 1848 I)

[161] H.6 "Vol. I 433-576 May to Nov 1848 Equatorial
+ Prime Vert. Laths."
↳ Lathwork of Obs?
Sat, Clocks in Here, Const/End
↳ Jup, Neptune.
↳ Uranus Satellites discovered

[162] H.7 "Vol. II 1-92 Magnetic, Fox Circle + Equatorial
1849 Feb. to June"
Jup.
(p. 20) Cont of Plates for Desc. of Obs.

[163] H.8 "Vol. II 93-192 Equatorial + Telegraph
"Early Printing Books"
Jan. to Nov. 1849"

(p.93) [Terms of Telegraph costs]
Arc. Cluster, Uranus, Mars

[164] H.10 "Vol II 193-292 Equatorial
From Dec. 1849 to April 1850"

* (inside cover): "Daguerreotyping w/
Great Refractor Commenced Dec. 18, 1849
(mom)

p.(217) - "The reasons why so few obs^s appear w/
the Great refractor are the following: "

[165] H.11 " Vol. II 293 - 392 Equatorial May 10 to Sept 1850 "

July 17 Day of a hyper
Parthenope, list of Aniels sent to
Dr. Gould for publication =
(p.382) - July 15

[166] H.12 " Vol II 393 - 488 Equatorial Sept 27, 1850 + Feb. 25, 1851

(p.397) Nov. 15, 1850 - New ring of Saturn
(p.400) Traveller at delay WCB on Meteor 1 Sept 51

[167] H. 13 " Vol II 489-584 Equatorial from Feb 25, 1851
to Dec. 4, 1851 "

[inside cover - Moon Day
Feb 6, 1851]

[14th March - Jupiter Day

[168] H. 14 " Vol III 1-98 Equatorial from Dec 4, 1851
to May 18, 1852 ^H/₃

[Encke's Comet]

[Feb. 26, 1852 - day. - Mars] etc.

[169] H. 15 " Vol III 99-194 Equatorial from May 19, 1852
to Oct. 26, 1852 "

(pp 131-2 Student's view)

[170] H. 16 " Vol III 195-288 eq. from Oct. 28 1852 to March 10, 1853
(Saturn)

[171] H. 17 " Vol III 289-388 ² eq. from Mar. 10, 1853 to Apr. 3, 1854 "

[172] H. 18 " Vol III 389 to 484 eq. Apr. 4, 1854 to Jan. 13, 1855 "

(Aug 25, Meteor)

(p. 400 - Aperture studies
(magnitudes)

Saturn, Magnetic

Disturbance

[173]

H. 19

"Equatorial Jan 13, 1855 to Apr. 1, 1856

Vol. ~~III~~ 484-574 "

(Saturn, Jap. Venus
Nov. 26 - Disappearance of Sat.)

[174]

H. 20

"Equatorial Apr 1, 1856 to Feb 15, 1857

Vol. V(2) 575-665 "

(p. 590 June 7 "As I was going
up to dome in dumb-waiter, and
Grove came down much faster
than I went up. I was only 2 feet
from the floor") (/ (/
"Saturn Eruptions"

[175]

H. 21

"6 Equatorial Feb 15, 1857 - May 13, 1857"

(Venus, Mercury, Saturn)

(March 4, 1857 "1st day of the (1st yr. of the
reign of James Buchanan, Pres. of
all the Un-States)

(March 31, Day begins again
(Apr. 3 - Black-chopped clouds)
(Measurements of Plates)

[176] H.22 "Equet. May 13, 1857 to Sept 1, 1857"
 (Photo. of Mizar)
 Aug 1, 1857 - Solar picture

[177] H.23 "Eg. Aug 23, 1857 - Oct. 22, 1857"
 (Comets, Jap. Exp. photo)

[178] H.24 "Eg. Oct. 23, 1857 to Dec. 14, 1857"
 (in ^{il} cover drawing)
 (Orion zones ABCD)

[179] H.25 "Eg. Dec. 1857 to March 1858"
 (Belvie ^{photo} March, 1858)
 (Orion Catalogue)

[180] H.26 "Eg. March 18, 1858 to July 13, 1858"
 (Jan 30 - Photo) - etc. ^{exp. in}

[181] H.27 "Eg. July 14 to Sept 25, 1858"
 (Comets - esp. Donat)

[182] H.28 "Eg. Sept 25 to Nov. 11, 1858"
 Donat Comet: Drawing by O.P.B. + de
 Oct 6 - Comet light polarized. ^{Obs}
 Feb. 21. 1859 - Letter to B. Reed from O.P.B.
 on Tail of Donat; Comet
 Comet Memoranda + photo.

[183] H.29 "Eg. Nov 11 1858 to May 4, 1859"
Jan 24, 1859 last obs of WCB
5 days before hid.

[184] H.30 "Eg. May 4 to Oct 26, 1859"
(July 25, 1859 - Solar Eclipse)

[185] H.31 "Eg. Oct 26, 1859 to Jan 31, 1860"
minor planets
Dec 28, '59 - Overseer.
Jan 20/31 - Photography

[186] H.32 "Eg. Jan 31, 1860 to March 14, 1860"
Up to Feb 8 - Photo
Feb 16 - new Reveler.
Mar. 2/3 Sup. Photometry
↑ exp. ments.
Mar. 9
Sup., Sat.

[187] H.33 "Eg. March 15, 1860 to March 25, 1860"
[Photometry; sup, Sat, etc]

[188] H. 34 "Eq. March 30, 1860 to May 2, 1860"

(Photometry; Jupiter + Moon)

Apr 24, 1860 - Moon Photo.

Apr. 12 - Sun Photo

Jupiter, Drawing

[189] H. 35 "Eq. May 2nd 1860 to June 22nd 1860"

(May 4 - Stars - etc.)

Photometry; Comets.

[190] H. 36 "Eq. June 24, 1860 To July 4, 1860" Comets

June 27 Comet Mook's traced graphically

July 23 Pendulum Experiments for Arctic Expedition

[191] H. 37 "Eq. July 4 to Sept 22, 1860"

Comets, Photometry

July 17/18 - Solar Eclipses

minor planets, Mars.

Meteor July 20, 1860
(letter)

Aug 1 - Lunar Photo.

[192] H. 38 "Eq. Sept. 26 1860 to Jan 30, 1861"

Pendulum Exp.

Occultation (↑ also above)

Minor Planets

Orion

~~July~~
~~July~~

[193] H.39 " Eq. Jan 31, to Apr. 8, 1861 "

Orion
Minor Planets.

[194] H.40 " Eq. Apr. 9, 1861 to May 2, 1861 "

Comets
New Planet

[195] H.41 " Eq. May 3 - June 22, 1861 "

"Owing to Moonlight, clouds &
Student's Planet (66) was in
danger of being lost."

[196] (H.42) " Eq. June 22, 1861 to July 13, 1861 " (Great Comet of 1861)

[197] H.43 " Eq. July 13 - Sept. 12, 1861 " (Great Comet)

[198] H.44 " Eq. Sept. 16 to Dec. 30, 1861 " Comets
Solar Eclipse Dec 30, 1861

[199] H.45 " Eq. Jan 1 - Apr. 18, 1862 "

Comets, Orion
Feb 1 1862. - Report of Discovery
of ^{4 1/2} " stars
of Sirius Company by A. Clark
(also Feb 7)
Minor Planets; Comets

[200] H.46 " Eq. Apr. 19, to July 5, 1862 " New Planet (Clyde) Sat, Jup
Comet

- [300] N. 17 " Vol 17 Oct 24 1869 - May 13, 1870"
(Meteor charts)
- [301] N. 18 ^{E₂} Misc. Obs. Vol 18 Oct 3, 1871 (to Nov. 27, 1871)"
- [302] N. 19 (Dec 24, 1869 - Sept 2, 1874) Misc. Obs.
- [303] N. 20 E₂ Dec 8, 1874 to July 11, 1875 Orig."
- [304] N. 21 "Asteroids from July 13, 1870 to Dec 21, 1870"
- [305] N. 22 "Obs of Asteroids from Feb 13, 1871 to Aug 10, 1871"
- [306] N. 23 "Search for Asteroids. As Lewis Trapp. Wm. A. Rogers Hunter + Trapp
(Setting stars)
- [307] N. 24 "Search for Asteroids"
- [308] N. 25 "Reduction of Asteroid Obs's. Differences of α and δ between
asteroids and comparison stars 1870."
- [309] N. 26 "Diff.'s of α + δ between asteroids & comp. stars
1870-71"
- [310] N. 27 "Reduction to apparent place of some comp stars used in 1870"

- [311] N. 28 "Reduction to 1870 of some Comp. stars"
- [312] No 29 "Reduction of some Asteroid Obs's 1870"
- [313] N. 30 "Search for Asteroids"
- [314] N. 31 "Obs's w/ E. E_g of Asteroids + Comets, from _____ to _____"
 (also star lists of 1855 + 1865) (copy)
 (also list of distances)
- [315] N. 32 "Computation of apparent place + differential refraction
 Reduction of E_g Comparisons. "Vol. 1"
 (June 30, 1866 - Apr. 26, 1868)
- [316] N. 33 "Reductions of E_g Obs's Oct 15, 1874 to June 2, 1875"
- [317] N. 34 "Obs's w/ E E_g (copy) Apr 9, 1866 - Aug 26, 1866, Vol. 1"
- [318] N. 35 "Obs's w/ E E_g (copy) Aug 27, 1866 to Oct 20, 1866 Vol 2"
- [319] N. 36 " _____ Oct 21, 1866 to Jan 14, 1867 Vol 3"
- [320] N. 37 " _____ Jan 14, 1867 - Apr. 26, 1867 Vol 4"

- July 11, 1867
- [334] 0.3 " East Transit May 31 - Nov 5, 1867" (w/ Frodsham's description of South Clock)
- [335] 0.4 " " Nov 9, 1867 - July 10, 1868"
- [336] 0.5 " " July 16, 1868 - Oct 2, 1868"
- [337] 0.6 " Obs's for Time w/ E. Transit 1868-1869" (Oct 3, 1868
Aug 22, 1869)
- [338] 0.7 " " 1869-1870" (Aug 29, 1869 -
June 6, 1870)
- [339] 0.8 " " June 12 1870, Jan 27, 1871"
- [340] 0.9 " Obs's for Time Dec 1-27 1871"
(for height purposes, Field observations, Moon Transit, South Clock
Henry Gannett - Observer)
- [341] 0.10 " Chronograph Record Apr. 1866² - July 29, 1867"
- [342] 0.11 " East Transit (Errors)" (Apr. 17, 1866 - Sept 17, 1867)
- [343] 0.12 " Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Cambridge 1867"
- [344] 0.13 " Transit Obs's 1867" - June 28, 1867 - June 29, 1867
- [345] 0.14 " Formula for reduction of transit obs's, drawn up about 1867" (+ tables)
- [346] ~~0.15~~ " Chronograph Record July 31 - Dec 17, 1867"
Also instrumental corrections to E. Transit level from July 31 - Oct 2

- [347] 0.16 "Chronograph record Dec 19, 1867 - Aug 14, 1868"
- [348] 0.17 "Chronograph record Aug 14, 1868 to (July 30, 1869)"
- [349] 0.18 "Aug 13, 1869 - July 7, 1870"
- [350] 0.19 "Records of errors of Clocks, transit instrument, etc. 1866-1869"
- [351] [0.20?] "Stars to be Observed w/ C. transit at Acad 1868-1870"
 (note in file: "Unlettered record Bk. received from Waterville in May, 1897. Prof Seale says belongs to Lewis O. to call it 020")
- [352] ~~0.20~~ "Second Computation of Index Errors for Reduction of Transit Obs's 1867-68. Account of the work of obs. & reduction, from Oct, 1867 to Dec, 1871. Plan for completing work"
- [353] ~~0.21~~ "Copy for HCO of long. Computations from Best Survey Obs's at the Obs. in 1869"
- [354] 0.22 "—" Aug 24, 1870 - Oct 23, 1870 (transit obs's)
- [355] 0.23 "Longitude 1871 - Field Reductions of Obs's at Cambridge" (mica window 6x3)
- [356] ~~0.24~~ "Clock Corrections 1869-1872"
- [357] 0.25 "Clock Corrections 1872-75"

- [358] O. 26 "Clock Connections" 1875 "
- * [359] O. 27 "Notes on the Astron. Engravings from ^{the} Obs. Phillips Fund
 Also, Spanish weather record, etc. See table
 of contents within; lists of apparatus, etc. (book costs, furniture)
- [360] O. 28 "Eclipse of 1869 Reports" (beautiful volume)
- [361] O. 29 "Personal Equator Obs's, 1871"
- [362] P. 1 "Magnetic Obs's Aug 16 1866 to Feb. 17, 1868"
- [363] P. 2 "Meteorological Obs's 1866. Although the diary is
 one made for 1865; the diary of the whole is corrected for 1866
 in the original entries, but the year is left uncorrected after May 7"
- [364] P. 3 "Recitation record w/ meteorological entries apparently of 1866"
- [365] P. 4 "Daily Journal for 1867" - (meteorological)
- [366] P. 5 "Daily Journal 1868" - "
- [367] P. 6 "Daily Journal for 1869" ✓
- [368] P. 7 " " " for 1870" ✓
- [369] P. 8 "Clayton's Dakota Diary 1871" ✓

[370] P. 9 "Daily Journal for 1872" (meteorological)

[371] P. 10 " " " " 1873 " "

[372] P. 11 Meteorological Record for 1874

[373] P. 12 " " " " 1875

[374] P. 13 "Met. Record for 1876 (Original)"

[375] P. 14 "Diary 1877" (met)

[376] P. 15 "Diary 1878" "

[377] P. 16 "Diary 1879" ✓

[378] Q. 1 "Met. Record for the years 1866, 1867, & 1868 with tables
+ avers"

~~378~~ [379] P. 2 ~~Meteorological Record~~ "Met Record of HEO 1869"

[380] Q. 3 "Met Record of HEO 1870, 1871"

[381] Q. 4 "Met Record of HEO for the yrs 1872 - 1877"

[382] Q. 5 "1878-1879. July to Dec 1866" (met Record)

[383] (Daniel Cox: "Mr. J. G. Homers' Original minutes of Worcester Equatorial Club
which will have historical value")

- [384] " (A - A_ of the White Mountains of New Hampshire 1853) " (Survey)
- [385] (Paris to Cambridge Telegraph) ^{Thurs} June 20 - July 12 (~1861)
- [386] " U.S. Coast Survey Bay Reserve Supt. : Letter Book + Abstract showing
deposition: made of bearings + reductions by the Longitude Party 1868 - "
- [387] " Obs + Long Computations " 1872. (U.S. Coast Survey)
- [388] " Long + Lat Res 1 " ("Bolivia") (1892-3)
- [389] " Time Service " ^{Apr 18} ~~(May 2)~~ 1880 - Apr 29, 1881
- [390] " Meridian Circle Record Mr Austin's record previous to Feb 27, 1871
(Aug 16, 1870 - May 13, 1871) "
- [391] " Record of the Photometric Observations " ^{Vol I} (March 6 - 1872 to March 21, 1872) C.S. Peirce
- [392] Vol ~~I~~ ^{II} April 22, - June 5, 1872
- [393] Vol ~~II~~ ^{III} June 6, - July 2, 1872
- [394] Vol ~~III~~ ^{IV} May 4, 1872 - May 30) Duplicate X)
- [395] Vol 5 May 31, - June 13, 1872) " etc.
- [396] Vol 6 June 10, - June 20, 1872)
- [397] Vol 7 June 30 - July 30, 1872)
- [398] Vol 8 July 30 - Aug 9, 1872)
- [399] Vol 9 Aug 9 - Sept 15, 1872
- [400] Vol 10 Aug 18 - '72 - Mar 7, '73

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duplicates
241-360

241	Red. of Z Obs's	1853	L. 3
242	"	1853	L. 4
243	"	1853	L. 5
244	"	1853	L. 6
245	"	1853 (54)	L. 7
246	"	1853/54 1855	L. 8
247	" (Comp.)	? (1855?)	L. 9
248	" Comp. of Mg.	1859	L. 10
249	" "	1859	L. 11
250	Special Zones + Mg's	1862 -	L. 12
251	Revision of Zones: Mg's	1860 (?)	L. 13
252	Reduction of Zones H.O.	1853	M. 2
253	Goold's Unusual Index (1848) (Book Index)		M. 3
254	Tables of Corrections (Personal)	? 1854 +	M. 5
255	Table of Contents of Various Obs. Books 1841-1855	(1866?)	M. 6
256	Various Memoranda	1842-1858	M. 7
257	Catalogue Stars	1854/58	M. 9
258	Tables for Appending Astronomical Corrections	1855	M. 10
259	Catalogue of Stars for Zones	1836-1850 (?)	M. 11
260	Red. of all the Stars in Urania (?)	1853, 1856	M. 12
261	Prints of Z.O's; Hist. & Descr. of Observing	1854	M. 13
262	Lists of Prizes + Distributions, Receipts of Annual of HCO	to 1875	M. 14
263	Metemological	1861/62	M. 15
264	Comet-Seeker	1859/60	M. 16
265	Oborodo Sunny: Time	1857/58	M. 17
266	" " : lat. by Polaris	1857/58	M. 18
267	Solar Obs. - Sunspots	1854/55	M. 19
268	Cent. of Bright Neb. + Clusters, obs.	1850/1853	M. 20
269	Comet Seeker (I. Bowditch)	1847/1850	M. 21
270	Books Received	1862 - 1878	M. 23

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271	Red. of Moon Culmination	1849 - 1852	M24
272	"	1851 - 1854	M25
273	P. S. N. (Zms?)	1854	M26
274	E; White Mt., Topoado	1849/51	M27
275	Gould's Univ. Index (of subscribers ^{to Society})	c. 1858	M28
276	Print. (plates) 1860 - 1862		M29
277	Memoranda for Observatory Report	1861/64	M30
278	Memoranda	1862/65	M31
279	Catalogue of Books in the Phillips library	1856 -	M32
280	Supp. Star list + obs's.	?	M33
			#
281	Trent Catalogue	c. 1863	M34
282	Edyrie (instru. tests)	c. 1846	M35
283	Account of various theorems + Papers of the Obs.	* to 1866/77	M36
284	Observations of Saturn, etc. (E. & E.)	1866	N1
285	E. E.	1866	N2
286	E E	1866	N3
287	E E	1866	N4
288	E E	1866	N5
289	E E	1866	N6
290	E E	1866	N7
291	EE	1866/67	N8
292	EE	1867	N9
293	E E	1867	N10
294	"	1867/68	N11
295	"	1868	N12
296	"	1868	N13
297	"	1868	N14
298	"	1868/69	N15
299	"	1869	N16
300	"	1869/70	N17

* give notebook plan to 77.

301	E.E.	1877/72	N18
302	(?) obs's. ^{comets} nebulae	1869/74	N19
303	"	1874/75	N20
304	Asteroids	1870	N21
305	"	1871	N22
306	" (W.A. Rogers)	?	N23
307	"		N24
308	Diff's of α and δ between Astron. + Stars	1870/71	N26
309	Red. of ast. obs's	1870	N25
310	No d. of apparent place of some comp. stars.	1870	N27
311	No d. to 1870 of some comp. stars.		N28
312	" some astral obs's.		N29
313	Search for Asteroids (1870)		N30
314	Obs. w/ E.E. of Ast. + Comets	c. 1866	N. 3
315	Comp. of app. places + differential refraction (Red. of E. Comp.)	c. 1866	N. 32
316	"	← 1874/75	N. 33
317	obs. w/ E.E.	1866	N34
318	"	1866	N35
319	"	1866/67	N36
320	"	1867	N37
321	"	1867	N38
322	"	1867/68	N39
323	"	1868	N40
324	Cent. of Nebulae (Search)		N41
325	Meas. of Phas's of Eclipse	1864-70	N42
326	" " " " Solar "	1870 ~	N43
327	Notes to sketches of $\odot$ by X. Trouvelot	1870/73	N44
328	"	1873/74	N45
329	Solar Photography	1870-76	N46
→ 330	General Record of (Works) Tables, etc. (Index etc.)	1869, 1872, 1866/77	N48 N50

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331	Red. measures of Del. Star. (EE)	1866/67	051
332	East Transit	1866	01
333	"	1866/67	02
334	"	1867	03
335	"	1867/68	04
336	"	1868	05
337	" (Obs.'s for Tunis)	1868/69	06
338	" "	1869/70	07
339	" " (Calculations)	1870/71	08
340	"	1871	09
341	Chronograph Record	1866/67	010
342	E. Transit (errors)	1866/67	011
343	Longitude Campaign (Cambridge-Washington)	1867	012
344	Transit Obs's	1867	013
345	Formula for Reduction of Transit Obs's	1867	014
346	Chron. Record; E.T. instrumental corrections	1867	015
347	"	1867/68	016
348	"	1868/69	017
349	"	1869/70	018
350	Records of errors of clocks, transit inst., etc.	1866-69	019
351	Stars to be Obs'd w/ E.T.	1868-70	020
352	^{2nd} Comput. of Inst. Error, (With outline)	1867/71	020
353	Long. Camp's from Coast Survey	1869	021
354	(Transit obs's?)	1870 71	022
355	Long. Reductions.	1871-	023
356	Clock Corrections	1869-72	024
357	Clock "	1872-75	025
358	"	1875	026
359	Notes on Arch. Engravings, etc.	1870/78	027
360	Eclipse of 1869; Reports	1869	028

[401] Vol. 11 (Duplicate) Mar 9 1873 - June 7, 1873.

[402] Vol. 12 (Duplicate) June 8 - July 1, 1873.

[403] Vol. 13 (Duplicate) Feb 6 - Sept 22, 1873.

[404] Vol. 14 (Dup.) Sept 22, - Sept 30, 1873.

[405] Vol. 15 (Dup) Sept 30 - Oct 11, 1873.

[406] Vol. 16 (Dup) Oct 11 1873 - Feb 10, 1874

[407] Vol. 18 (Dup) Apr 13 - May 3, 1874

[408] Vol 19 (Dup) May 20, - July 15, 1874

[409] Vol. 20 (Dup.) July 17 - Aug 2, 1874

[410] Vol 21 (Dup) Aug 3 - Aug 4, 1874

[411] Vol. 22 (Dup) Aug 22 - Nov 26, 1874

[412] Vol. 23 (Dup) Nov 26 - Dec 21, 1874

[413] Vol. 24 ~~(Dup)~~ Dec 21, 1874 - Jan 14, 1875

[414] Vol 25 & [May 28, 1875]

[415] (paper folder) "Index to Books on Meridian Circles
Work 1870-1876"

[416] "Fundamental Steps for Zones from Mar 17, 1873 - Dec 1, 1873
B8"

(F25)
[417] "General Catalogue. Obs's + Reductions. Final Reductions.
B1"

(F9) observed w/ Mer. Circle in 1871-2
[418] Fundamental Steps. Obs's + Reductions. Final values.
B, 1870-71.
From $0^{\text{h}} 2^{\text{m}} 10^{\text{s}}$ to $14^{\text{h}} 10^{\text{m}}$ "

(F58)
[419] Mrs. Mays Comparison Stars. ARCADE Comp. Stars.
Obs's + Reduc's 1877."

(K-8)
[420] "Flexure Constants. Equatorial Point Corrections. 1874-5"

(CK-11)
[421] "Instrumental Constants 1870-71 Depending on the new
Pulkova Places"

[422] "Baromet. Thermomet. Runs,
Collimation, Flexure" (Nov. 10, 1870 - Feb 7, 1879)

[423] (K-25) "Refraction Constants. $B + T + \gamma$ From Apr 10, 1870 to Feb 2, 1886"

[424] (M-2) "Obs's w/ Mer. Circle in Zone 50° to 55° .
Zone Stars obs'd Nov 16, 1870 to Dec 16, 1876.

[425] (M-3) (as above) Zone 50 to 55°
Zone Stars obs'd Dec. 16, 1870 - March 25, 1871 "

[426] (M-21) Misc. Tables. Formulae for Zone Reductions. (1870-71)

[427] (M-29) "Misc Obs's. Merid. of Venus, Longitude Montreal - Cambridge"
(1883)

[428] (P-1) "Obs's of Tempel's Comet May 19 - July 22, 1873
and of Astronoids Nos 109, 112, 121 + 331 May 18 - Dec 22,
Periods of Ruling Machine Screws (Apr 9?) to May 10, 1877" (1873)

[429] (P-2) "Preliminary Investigation of Ruling Machine Screws
Disc. of Astronoid No. 112 (Dyhegenia) Elements + Ephemeris 1873-4
+ No. 109 (Felicite) Ephemeris 1875-6"

[430] (P-3) "Astronoid 109. Elements + Ephemeris 1877-8"

[431] (P-6) "Discussion of Orbit of Felicite + Dyhegenia" (109) (112) 1871-4

[432] (102) (Pencil for work - ~1877)

[433] (P-8) "Planetary Positions (Helio-centric) Sat, Ur, Nept, Jup - 1750 to 1860

[434] (P-9) (~1871) Stars lists (Zones)

(J23)(A4)

[435] " Chromograph Record May 27, 1880 to Oct 5, 1880 " (Description of set-up)

[436] " Absolute Work Star List - Final List of Dates of Obs. See Index. " (1879-1881) (John A. Dunne 1906)

[437] " Abs. Work Meridian Circle Obs. 1879-1881 " (Notebook A W) (Anna Winlock) (Rogers Obs. Work)

[438] " Abs. Work. Notebook S.C.B. " Selma C. Bond (1898-1907) (1879-1881)

[439] " Posting Book Oct 1-1897 - " (1908) (Indexed) (Index of Four Obs. etc.)

[440] " Rogers' Abs. Work: Notebook J. A. Dunne " 1904-1911

[441] (T-1) " Special light Curves with Photometer " - (1895-1896)

[442] (T-3) (Variable Stars - ~ 1897)

[443] (T-4) " Ephemerids of Variable Stars " (1896-1898)

[444] (T-5) " Meast. of Comp. Stars for Variables w/ Photometer " (1895-1901)

[445] (T-14) (Variables) 1897 - 1898

[446] I " (West equatorial) Obs. of Variable Stars by W^m. Maxwell Reed "

1890 - 91

[447] II " 1891 -

[448] III " 1891 - 1892

[449] IV 1892 -

[450] V 1892 - 1893

[451] VI West Eg Record W.M. Reed 1894 - 1895

[452] VI West Eg / on + After Feb. 11, 1894
Abbott Academy Telescope 5 1/6 " aperture"
1893 - 1894

[453] VIII 1896 - 1898

[454] IX 1898 - 1900

[455] 1900 -

[456] H. R. Colson, Jr. Notebook of His Obs.
(West Eg.)

Apr. 10, 1899 - Feb. 9, 1902

S. S. Cys, Nova Herii.

Migrating birds, (Sept 25, 1901)

[457] W. Eg. Obs. Apr. 10, 1898 - May 17, 1899 S. S. Cys.

[458] Eg. Work - Meas. of Light of Neb + ex of spectrum.
etc.
→ Record of 72 blocs. (R)

[459] Index (R)
also lists of Variables, etc. (Objects)
(Jup. Satell. Ec.)

[460] Index (R)

[461] (1877, Aug. 16) — Nathaniel Millimeter Plate Measurements
(N17) to July 25, 1882) etc.

[462] (N18) Meteor. Obs'n. etc. Sighting of Mountains.
Historical
June 23, 1880 — Aug. 20, 1885

[463] Aug - Sep. 1877 (R. 19) — Planetary Planometry
(Mrs. Sch. Jpn.)
Sketches "

[464] (R. 20) Aug. '877 - Oct., 1877
Sat. Mars

[465] R. 22 . Ceti, λ Cyg, δ Can., β Perse.
1838 up to 1854

[466] R. 23 1877 - 1879

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467 (R24) Photometric Red's. 1877

468 (R25) Ephemerides of Saturn's Satellites + Jovian's. etc. Obs.

469 Errors of Girdes(?) of W Eg. 1877-78 (R26) + Misc. Obs.

470 Misc. Obs + Red.? c. 1878 (R28)

471 1870-72 (Summary of V&S?) (R29)

472 5 1877 } Photometric Obs. (R30)

473 6 1878 } (R31)

474 c. 1878 R32

475 (1879-81 Obs. + Lists. (R33)

476 Form for Eg. Obs. 1879 (R34)

EC P? } Prospective Work + Proposed Form of Publication. 1874-81 (R35)

W Eg } 7 1878 (R43)

479 8 1878 (R44)

480 14 1879

W. G. Eastwood

481 1878-79 Photometric Obs's w/ W. E. (1046)

482 ↑ - + Obs's

483 Desc. of Venus Obs procedures + Opt. Set ups.

484 C. 1879 ↑ + other Obs's (PN del.)

485 1879-80 ↑

486 1879 ↑

487 1879-80 Planets + Planet Obs's

488 Eclip.'s of Jup. Satell. 1878-9

489 J. R. Edmonds 1881 Comp. of Eye + Photm. Est. of Sts. Meas.

490] Comet Reductions #1 1881

491 #2 1880-83

492 26 1881-82

493 1882 (28)

494 6 1/4" Clay 1882-83

495 (15")-1884

496 1882-88 Comets 5*

497 1882-85 Comets

498 1883-87 Comets

499 (? 15") Eg. 1885

500 1882-89 Comets (Parallax Comp)

- 501 1882-94 Comets.
- 502 1883-87 Comets
- 503 1885-88 Comets.
- 504 1888-89 Comets.
- 505 1889-98 Copies of ~~the~~ Telegrams ^{of} Comets
- 506 1890 Comets (10)
- 507 1889-90 Comets (9)
- 508 1889-91 RW Bifford Journal (Const. of Dome, etc 22)
- 509 55 1890
- 510 59 1891
- 511 (51) Agassiz + Zodi. Light Obs. (Bologna) 1891-92
- 512 (11) 1891-92 Comets
- 513 AED's Journal (Bologna) # 2 1891-94 (56)
- 514 62 1892
- 515 1892-99 Comets
- 516 Parallel-Computed # 2 1891-93 (Comets)
- 517 1892 Comets + ~~the~~ (US) obs.
- 518 Comets 1892-97 (#13?)
- 519 6? 1892-3
- 520 67 1893

521	68	1893-4	PP 81	2V	
522	69	1894	1881	2V	
523	70	1894	50-2101	2V	
524	72	1894	1091-0001	(2V)	
525	A E Douglas's Journal #3		1893-5	(5)	(Cantel)
526	(Clymer)	1894-5	VS		
527	7(3)?	1894-5			
528	76	1895			
529	VS	1895-1898	6" W Eg		
530	77	1895			
531	79	1896			
532	80	1896			
533	81	1896			
534	VS ¹	W.B. Clymer Clymer (Arizona)	1895-98		
535	AC	1895-98			
536	(85?)	1896			
537	(AC I)	VSO	1895-99		
538	Charles P Howard	1897-1911	Telescope Mech. units + Golf Scores		
539	94	1897-98			
540	AC II	1898-1900			

541	VS	1899		
542	VSOB's	1891	] S I Bealy	
543	VSOB's	1899-02		
544	(AJC)	1900-1901		
545	122 (122)	1901		
546	123	1901		
547	124	1902-1905	H.R. Colson - Notebook # 2	
548	125	1901-1905		
549	126	1901		
550	127	1901		
551	(128)	1901		
552	129	1901-2		
553	130	1902		
554	131	1902		
555	132	1902		
556	133	1902		
557	134	1902		
558	135	1902-3		
559	136	1903		
560	137	1903		

561	138	1903	FOPI	FOPI	182
562	139	1903	FOPI	FOPI	182
563	140	1903	FOPI	FOPI	182
564	141	1903	FOPI	FOPI	182
565	142	1903-4	FOPI	FOPI	182
566	143	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
567	144	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
568	145	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
569	146	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
570	147	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
571	148	1904	FOPI	FOPI	182
572	149	1904-5	FOPI	FOPI	182
573	150	1905	FOPI	FOPI	182
574	151	1905	FOPI	FOPI	182
575	152	1905	FOPI	FOPI	182
576	153	1905	FOPI	FOPI	182
577	154	1905-6	FOPI	FOPI	182
578	155	1906	FOPI	FOPI	182
579	156	1906	FOPI	FOPI	182
580	157	1906	FOPI	FOPI	182

581	158	1906	2001	251
582	159	1906-7	2001	251
583	160	1907	2001	251
584	161	1907	2001	251
585	162	1907	2001	251
586	163	1907	2001	251
587	164	1907-8	2001	251
588	165	1908	2001	251
589	166	1908	2001	251
590	167	1908	2001	251
591	168	1908	2001	251
592	169	1908	2001	251
593	170	1908-9	2001	251
594	171	1909	2001	251
595	172	1909	2001	251
596	173	1909	2001	251
597	174	1909	2001	251
598	175	1909	2001	251
599	176	1909-10	2001	251
600	177	1910	2001	251

601	178	1910			
602	179	1910			
603	180	1910-11			
604	181	1911			
605	182	1911			
606	183	1911			
607	184	1911-1912			
608	185	1912			
609	186	1912			
610	187	1912			
611	15 th Record	1912-13 (not numbered)	- included in 'Family Records' by EC Archiving - 10/2/87		
612	188	1912-15			
613	189	1915-16			
614	190	1916			
615	191	1916			
616	192	1916			
617	193	1916			
618	194	1916-17			
619	195	1917			
620	196	1917			

621	↑ 197	1917		
622	198	1917		
623	199	1917-18		
624	200	1918		
625	201	1918		
626	202	1918-19		
627	203	1919-20		
628	# 204	1920-23	(#204)	
629		1926-27	(#205)	
630		1928-30	(#206)	
631		1934-35	(#207)	
632		1935-36	(#208)	
633		1936	(#209)	
634		1936	(#210)	
635		(also 12" Nav)	1936-39	(#211)
636	15" E _g	1936-37	(#212)	
637	12"	1914	(#1) - mostly blank, others in series not numbered,	
638	12"	1915-16		
639	12"	1916-17		
640	12"	1917-18		

641	12"	1919	
642	[Box of papers]	II Meteors (chems) 1898-99	Orig. Obs. + Preliminaries
643	12"	1919-20	[see W.I. Fisher file] (2 record books + papers)
644		1920	
645		1920-21	
646		1921	
647	US Obs's	1921	
648		1921	
649		1921-22	
650		1922	
651		1922	
652		1922-23	
653		1923	
654		1923	
655		1923-24	
656		1924	
657		1924-25	
658		1925	
659		1925-26	
660	12"	1925-26	

661	12"	PIPI	1926-27
662	12"	(normal) metal II	1927
663	12"	05-PIPI	1927-28
664	12"	05PI	1928-29
665	12"	15-05PI	1928-33
666	12"	UT. 1 Obs. 2.	1934-5
667	12" Polar	15PI 15PI	1935-6
668	1	15PI	1905-6
669	3	55-15PI	1907
670	4	5PI	1907-8
671	5	55PI	1908-9
672	6	25-55PI	1909
673	7	55PI	1909
674	8	55PI	1909-10
675	#9	24" LC & Obs.	1910-11
676	1	Photometric Obs CS Beire	1872
677	2	25-45PI	1872
678	3	25PI	1872
679	4	25-75PI	1873
680	5	25-75PI	1873

681	Vol 6	1874	
682	Vol 7	1874	
683	Vol 8	1874-5	
684	Experiments w/ Photometer	Peirce	1872
685	Leah B Allen	η Centauri (Spectral study)	1911 (notes; 1940-42)
686	# 1	CJA	Clusters $\rightarrow$ Spectro photometric tracing c 1930
687	# 2		} 1930-36 (?) traces of α Cys + Vega
688	# 3		
689	# 4		
690	# 5		
691	# 6		
692	# 1	Misc.; V;	
693	# 2	1918-19	V. (Map of the sky)
694	# 4	1919	Map of the sky; V; Sequences for Orion Neb.
695	# 5	M.D. Applegate	Asteroids + Novae 1919-20
696	# 6	1920-21	Nov + V
697	MDA #7	1920-21	Map of the sky (Novae?)
698		Bailey 1889-90	Daily Journal (1889-90)
699	# 25	S.D. Bailey	Obs. of D ₁ Stars + Planets 1894-96 (13 th Ann. Boyden)
700	# 1	DWB (Wilhelmia)	1917-19 Misc + Var's.

Carol Jane Anger

701	# 2	Spectrum Work	1917-19
702	# 3	Dwight W Block + FO Ceti chart, Nov. 3	1917-19
703	# 4	Variables	1918-19
704	# 6	Asteroids	1918-19
705	# 7	DW Block - Variables	1919
706	FE Byasch # 1		1903 (US + Metens)
707	1	1896-98 S E Ponslin	
708	2	1898	
709	3	1898	
710	4	1899	
711	5	1901-2	
712	6	1902	
713	7	1902-3	
714	8	1903	
715	9	1903	
716	10	1903	
717	11	1903	
718	12	1903-4	
719	13	1904	
720	14	1904	

721	15	1904	
722	16	1904	
723	17	1904	
724	18	1904-5	
725	19	1905	
726	20	1905	
727	21	1905-6	
728	22	1906	
729	23	1906	
730	24	1906	
731	25	1906	
732	26	1906	
733	27	1907	
734	28	1907	
735	29	1907	
736	30	1907-8	
737	(31)	1908	
738	32	1908	
739	#33	1909	
740	SEB # 34	(1909-10)	

Obs books
(VS)

741	SEB ^{±35}	1910-11	US	alt	
742	SEB(?)	1903	Magr. Estimates	(#4??)	
743	L. A. Bingham	1922	(Camp) for US		
744	G. R. Brooke	1919	(US?)		
745	II	1901-1902			LC
746	III	1902-1903			
747	IV	1903			US
748	V	1903-4			
749	VI	1904			
750	VI VII	1904-5			
751	IX		1905-07		
752	X		1907-8		
753	XI	5"	1908-9		
754	XI	LC 5"	1909-11		
755	LC Obs		1903-6		
756	Journal of Obs made w/ Phot X in 5" (LC)		1903-5		
757	1905	LC			
758	1906-7	LC #2			
759	Photometric Obs's	1915	LC		
760	6" Eq. (West)	1917-24	(LC)		

- 761 Memoranda on V.S.'s 1904-5 LC
- 762 8" Paler Telescope I 1908-9 LC
- 763 " " II 1909-11 LC
- 764 VS Obs 1911-1912
- 765 Obs. of VS 1912-14 LC
- 766 S I 8 17 1911-12 (Pyr.?) (LC?) ✓
- 767 Photometer Records 1913-15
- 768 Van Star Obs 1914-15 (L.C.) ✓
- 769 Log Book of the Argentine Station of the HCO 1915
- 770 #17 413
- 771 Pyheliometer Obs (17) 1914
- 772 Estimate of Work 1911 (obs sig in Peru)
- 773 Southern V.S. (LP) 1910
- 774 1907-1909 Ver. (ESM) (HEB) (KL)
- 775 L.P. Southern Var's (Ver. Obs.) 1904-1908
- 776 I ↑ 1918
- 777 II Nova Aquilae No. 3 1918 Henr Campbell
- 778 —
- 779 Henr Campbell VS Obs's 1900-1901 (Ver.)
- 780 iv 1901-2

- 781 $\rightarrow$ (1902-3)
- 782 $\rightarrow$ V
- 783 $\rightarrow$ VI 1903-4
- 784 $\rightarrow$ VII 1904
- 785 $\rightarrow$ VIII 1904-5
- 786 $\rightarrow$ IX 1905-9
- 787 $\rightarrow$ X 1906-7
- 788 $\rightarrow$ A>C XI 1907-1909
- 789 $\rightarrow$ A>C Notes for Readings (101) 1911-1935
- 790 $\rightarrow$ A.J. Cannon - 1912-1935 Guest Book
- 791 $\rightarrow$ Seth C. Chandler 1862 - 1882 No Stars; long Detem.
- 792 C.A. Chant W. Vignier I (1916)
- 793 C.T. Chase 1926^T M's of the Development of Spectral Lines in Stars in the red region
- 794 P.D.1 M's of Spectra of Novae 1926
- 795 P.D.2 Paul Davidovich Measurements of Line Intensity in Shell Spectra
- 796 [72] The Journal of A.E. Douglas 1896 Lat + long Work
- 797 Radiometric Book I 1937-38
- 798 Radiometry II Emerson 1939-40
- 799 Radiometric Program Book I E.M. Brown 1936-38
- 800 1937-38 Galvanometer Book I. (to go w/ Radiometric Book I)

Visual Obs^r

11360-1099

Bound Books

801	WPF 1	1890-92	Var. Stars.	(15)
802	2	1892-94	Var. Stars	
803	3	1892-94	Var. Stars, Spectra	
804	4	1893-98	Var. Stars	
805	5	1894-95	Var. Stars	
806	6	1895-99	Var. Stars, Spectra	
807	7	1895-96	Var. Stars.	
808	8	1896	Var. Stars.	
809	9	1896-97	Var. Stars.	
810	10	1897-98	Var. Stars	
811	11	1897-1902	Var. Stars.	
812	12	1898-1903	Var. Stars,	
813	13	1898-1905	Var. Stars	
814	14	1899-1905	Var. Stars.	
815	15	1903-1907		
816	16	1904-1910	Comp. Star (also similar from German Obs.)	
817	17	1905-1908	Var. Stars (w/Photo)	
818	18	1906-11	Moving Comets, Spectra	
819	19	1908-11	Sp. Obs. + ^{also} Mex. Obs.	
820	20	↑ 000339-095659		

W.P. Fleming

100661-185905

- 821 (21) ↑
- 822 WPF 22 Ledger of my - Record - Variables - Sp 190048 - 235939
- 823 (WPA) cluster + Fair Stems. (23) 1904 (11) C
- 824 Mrs. Fleming - Nov. Paper Reductions, 1902
- 825 WPF - V. Stems. (29)
- 826 Mrs. Fleming - Measurements of Bright-line Spectra, 1890
- 827 2
- 828 3 1886-7
- 829 4 1886
- 830 5 1886
- 831 6 1886-7
- 832 7 ↑
- 833 8 1886-7
- 834 9 1886-7
- 835 11 ↑ 1887
- 836 12 ↑ 1887
- 837 13 ↑ 1887
- 838 14 ↑
- 839 15 ↑ 1887
- 840 16 R ↑ 1887

- | | | | |
|-----|----|-------------------------------------|--|
| 841 | 17 | ↑ | 1887 |
| 842 | 18 | ↑ | 1887-88 |
| 843 | 19 | ↑ | 1887 |
| 844 | 20 | ↑ | 1887-89 |
| 845 | 21 | | Red's of Photo. Ob's. |
| 846 | 22 | | Cat. of E Stars. |
| 847 | 23 | ↑ | 1887-88 |
| 848 | 24 | | Desc. of Spectra. 1887-89 |
| 849 | 25 | ↑ ^E | (12) |
| 850 | 26 | | Cat. of E Stars. |
| 851 | 27 | | Discordant Spectra, (Also) Remains in Rejected Measures. |
| 852 | 28 | G ↑ | |
| 853 | 29 | E St. St. a " Sp. Pl. | |
| 854 | 30 | Desc. of Spectra | |
| 855 | 31 | G Standard Stars on Spect. Plates | |
| 856 | 32 | Descr't. of Spectra | 1888-90 |
| 857 | 33 | C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates | |
| 858 | 34 | Catalogue of J Plates | |
| 859 | 35 | Red's of Photo. Ob's. | 1888-90 |
| 860 | 36 | F + G | Discordant Spectra |

- 861 39 Red. of Photogr. Obj's
- 862 40 ~~80-1881~~ $\uparrow$ N, H, L $\uparrow$ $\uparrow$ c. 89
- 863 41 Cent. of Plates Classes C, D Previous Plates c. 89
- 864 42 ~~17-1881~~ $\uparrow$ Southern + a few Northern Plates c. 1889
- 865 45 Obj's of Interest on Spectra Plates c. 1890
- 866 97 (see 900) WDF (Southern) 98-07
- 867 (49) Misc. 1890-9/9 (Ed., Subs., etc.)
- 868 50 Disc. of Dr. Cat.
- 869 Meas. of Sp. Plates SD Cat (51) 1890-92
- 870 Desc. of Sp. Meas. for SD Cat. 1890/1893
- 871 53 Discussion of Dr. Cat.
- 872 56 "
- 873 57 " $\uparrow$ 14 (8")
- 874 58 $\uparrow$ (8" Dryer in Cambr.)
- 875 59 Cat of best Plates (Bache in ^{telescope} Peru)
- 876 61 1892
- 877 62 1872-1893
- 878 63 1893
- 879 64 1893
- 880 65 1893

881	67	1893
882	68	1893
883	69	1893 - 1894
884	70	1894 - 1903
885		1893 - 94
886	Dr. Ca. Spectra Class C Dr. Ca. Spectra	
887	Desc. of Spectra Measured for Dr. Ca. 1894 - ^{1903 to} 1904	
888	① (III Type (red?) stars)	
889	②	
890	Slender Parallel Stars (13"), var. So. Stars lists c. 1893 in before.	
891	Spectra to be Compared in List of III Stars. (3)	
892	Constants S. D. Cat.	
893	Red's of Plates Having less than 4 Standard Stars.	
894	(15) Notes on Dr. Cat.; Accounts of the Share-Holders of the Camera 5/92	
895	81	1903 - 4
896	82	1903
897	83	Measures of Sp. Plates (Smith. Dreyer Cat.) 1903 - 1904
898	96	Ponce Spectrum Plates 1896 - 1909
899	No. 98	Meridian 1898 - 1911
900	No. 99 Obs's of Interest in Southern Bache Plates WPF 1897-1911 10.2-11	

From Dreyer mem.

- 960 37 Misc. ↑ + Calib. Meas. 12/1/14 - 8/5/16
- 961 38 Catalogues (Compin Stars) 5/24/15 - 4/2/19
- 962 39 Misc. (Uen) 10/20/15 - 11/18/19
- 963 40 Discovery of New Variables 1/22/16 - 7/24/20
- 964 #41 Misc. (esp. Uen) 5/6/16 - 1/19/20
- 965 #43 Standard Magnitudes 9/30/19 - 6/4/21
- 966 H.S.L. #44 (XLIV) Misc. (Uen) * 1/20/20 - 10/3/21
- 967 #1 Misc. Obs. Book Ver. 3/24/93 - 2/6/96
- 968 #2 Ver's (5M) 2/7/96 - 4/23/96
- 969 #3 Ver's (5M) 4/23/96 - 12/31/96
- 970 #4 MS, + calibr. meas. 4/25/96 - 2/15/97
- 971 #5 Ver's in SM Sarp. 1/1/97 - 6/24/98
- 972 (EFLeland #7 Observing Book): Ver's in W Cen 11/8/97 - 1/22/98¹
- 973 EFL #15 Measures of Eros (South Pole), 3/3/99 - 12/23/02

* RU Sagittari (10/6) (c. 1905)

ESK = E. S. King

LH = L. Hofnagel

WSF = W. S. Franks

ASL = A. S. Leard

KG

BPG = B. P.

GH = G. H. Hill

11365

MEH = ^{Hauke} M. E. Harriman

EH = E. Hoag

MH = Margaret Harwood

CPH = Charles P. Howard

MAH or AH = Alberta Hawes

MH = Mary Howe

901	Variables & Halley's Comet	WSF	1909-10	1
902	Colours of 2149 southern stars	WSF	1910	
903	Variables	BPG		1
904	"	BPG	1912-1929	2
905	"	BPG	1900-1920	3
906	"	BPG	1899-1927	4
907	Spectrophometry of Band O stars	BPG		5
908	New Variables	BPG	¹⁸⁹⁹ 1900 - 1919	6
909	Color indices of long period variable	BPG		7
910	Spectrophometry ^{B stars} with Rayet stars	BPG		8
911	Variable stars	BPG	1900-1927	9
912	B star observations	MEH	1902	
913	Journal of MC Plates ^{Taken for Determination} of standard Magnitude	MEH	1908	
914	Measurements of variable stars	MH	1908	
915	Measure estimates of widths of A+B stars	MAH	1922	
916	Assorted plate measurements	MAH	1912-1918	4
917	5" Equatorial	MAH	1918	
918	Variable stars	ASL & GH	1904-6	1
919	Various star observations	EH	1889-1916	
920	Color connection for Telescope objectives	CPH	1878	
921	Assorted plate measurements			
922	" " "	LH	1928-1930	
923	Measurements of plates, stars, etc.	ESK	1895-98	1
924	Reductions of Measures	ESK	1899- 90	2
925	Notes pertaining to photographic instruments	ESK	1904-24	3
926	Assorted measurements, distances, altitudes, ^{plates}	ESK	1901-02	3
927	Assorted plate measurement	ESK	1902	4
928	Color distance measurements	ESK	1920	5
929	Schilt Photometry	ESK	1927-8	6
930	Photographic Measurement of light		1897	

HSL = H S Leavitt

931	Computation Book No 2 Beginning at Tagr 65	ESK	1916	
932	Photographic Magnitudes, Miscellaneous	HSL	1914-18	1
933	Variables, observations	HSL	1902-3	2
934	Examination of Plates	HSL	1903	4
935	variables	HSL	1903	5
936	Phoebe	HSL	1904	
937	Curcum Polar Variables	HSL	1895-6	1
938	Various Star Observations	HSL	1896	2
939	" " " & Plate measurements	HSL	1896	3
940	Assorted plate measurements & Star ^{various} obser-	HSL	1896	4
		HSL		5
941	Star Observations, Measurements	HSL	1902	5
942	Curcum polar variables	HSL	1902-4	6
943	Star Observations	HSL	1904	7
944	Misc. Observations	HSL	1904-10	9
945	" "	HSL	1906-16	13
946	Discovery of New Variables	HSL	1907-8	22
947	Comparison stars	HSL	1906-7	23
948	Observations of New Variables	HSL	1906-7	24
949	" " " "	HSL	1907-14	25
950	Standard Photographic Magnitudes. 7 Plates	HSL	1907-9	26
951	" " "	HSL	1908-10	27
952	" Magnitudes	HSL	1909-11	28
953	" Photographic Magnitudes: 30. Pole	HSL	1910-12	29
954	" " "	HSL	1910	30
955	" " "	HSL	1911-14	32
956	Miscellaneous Journal	HSL	1911-12	33
957	Miscellaneous	HSL	1911-14	34
958	Objects looked up by Request	HSL	1914-18	35
959	Standard Magnitudes	HSL	1914-19	36
960				

- Faint
- 985 (#38) Measure (Scale for portions of stars) 8/22/10 - 10/6/11
- 984 (#35) " 8/6/10 - 5/29/12
- 983 (#37) " 10/6/11 - 6/25/12
- 982 (#34) 2/20/07 - 3/5/10 (with 2 p. of in the dust
3/19/10 from E.C.P. d.ing
9/5/10)
- 981 (#33) Search for variable measures (Scale)
(3/22/04 - 5/13/10)
- 980 (#31 or 32) → 3/20/07 - 4/26/09
- 979 (#30) ↓ 5/19/04 to 1/26/07
- 978 (#28) " 3/28/03 to 4/30/04
- 977 (#27) 12/31/02 - (3/27/03)
- 976 (#26) Measure of Error 6/24/02 - 11/25/04 E.C. P. note 1 p. 4/24/02
- 975 (#25) " M3 etc. 5/17/02 - 2/2/03
- 974 (#16) (Plunder) " of New Sect. of Saturn; Nova Jgiffari 3/16/99 - 3/26/06
- 973 (#15)

KG 11365

Series Reduction. mostly ME plates

- 999 ↓ EFL (#51) 9/2/15 - 4/28/17 (ScV[↓], ScM) Sculp?
- 998 (#50) 6/2/15 - 4/10/17 " +ScP
- 997 (#49) 2/19/15 - 12/11/17 ScW
- 996 (#48) 5/8/14 - 7/5/15 U
- 995 (#47) 2/10/14 - 5/8/15
- 994 (#46) 12/30/13 - 1/14/15
- 993 (#45) 9/27/13 - 5/5/14
- 992 (#44) ^(5/17/13) 10/8/14 - 6/23/15
also Variables in M5

- 991 (#43) 4/4/13 - 10/8/14
- 990 (#42) 3/3/13 - 11/10/13
- 989 S.P. ↓ (#41) [Observing Book (M5) 1/15/13 - 5/15/13]
- 988 ↓ (#40) 1/8/13 - 6/4/13
- 987 (#39) 8/12/12 - 1/13/13
- 986 (#38) 6/15/12 - 6/28/12

E. F. Leland